

MADRAS

D5.15 Communication Materials

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Executive summary

EUT is responsible for designing and implementing the MADRAS communication strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners have been involved in it. This deliverable details the communication materials that have been prepared from M1-M12 including, among others, the development of the project's visual identity, the production of project website and digital dissemination and promotional materials, social media activity, the press release written and the newsletters subscription campaign. An evaluation of media impacts, as well as social media statistics is included.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>IME</i>	<i>In Mold Electronics</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Image</i>

Introduction

MADRAS is a 3-year research project aiming to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, developing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).

The project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of a robust series of plasronics' products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster uptake.

In addition, MADRAS project proposes two products for the users' authentication market and smart manufacturing, which will show a step forward towards digitisation and Internet of Things for its contribution to the sustainable deployment of smart products for consumer use.

EUT is the partner leader of **Task 5.7 Communication Activities**, but all consortium partners are involved in it. Task 5.7 has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.

(http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

Communication materials

During the first year of the project, EUT as the leader of Communication task has produced and designed **different types of communication materials** and carried out **communication activities** aiming at disseminating the project and catch the attention of both the scientific community and the industrial community, as well as the non-specialised audience about the potential benefits and impact of the research done in MADRAS.

The communication materials developed during this period (M1-M12) include the creation of MADRAS's corporate visual identity, project's website and social media channels and the production of different promotional materials and a press release, among others.

Figure 1: MADRAS Communication materials and activities

The following sections present and detail the main communication materials and tasks that have been done during the first year of MADRAS project by EUT with the collaboration of all the consortium.

1. Project's corporate visual identity

According to the work plan, EUT has developed MADRAS's Visual Corporate Identity (VCI), aimed at **properly aligning all communication materials across all the project's tasks**.

The Visual Corporate Identity includes the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards' guidebook, which defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS, including the different uses of the logo, corporate colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources.

See **D5.9 Visual Corporate Image** for more information and details of the Visual Corporate Identity designed and implemented.

Figure 2: MADRAS full colour logo

Figure 3: View of some pages of the project's deliverable template

Figure 4: Some graphic resources designed for MADRAS project

2. Public Website

On M3 (June 2020) MADRAS's project website (www.madras-project.eu) was launched, with the objective to serving as the main information channel for users interested in learning more about the project.

The website is the **main anchor for all communication activities related to the project and serves as a central point of entry for all public material**, including the basic information, main results achieved and public materials. The website is regularly updated with new information about MADRAS and conferences or exhibitions attended by the consortium.

MADRAS's website follows the corporate visual identity of the project and gives access to its social media channels (Twitter and YouTube).

Deliverable **D5.10 - Public Project Website**, submitted in Month 3 - 30th June 2020) summarises and details the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

Figure 5: Current website structure

2.1 Analytics M3-M11

The MADRAS website has Matomo installed on the platform’s back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site’s performance. Since its launch in M3, the website has received **694 visits**, **1,919 page visits** coming from **403 users** and **3 actions per visit** including **page views**, **downloads**, **outlinks** and **internal site searches** (*analysis based on M3 - website creation until February 2021*).

As for geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits have come from Spain (denoting EUT’s own efforts disseminating and communicating it at the Spanish level). The following figure seems relevant also to show that MADRAS has impacted beyond EU borders.

Figure 6: Top 6 visitor location per num. of visits and visitor map (June 2020 - February 2021).

Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices. On the other hand, **top viewed pages** include the homepage, about the project's page and the consortium section.

Figure 7: Top 5 most viewed pages and device types per visit

2.2 New pages created

2.2.1 Media page

This page was created around M7 (October 2020) when the first project press release was produced and sent to partners' media contacts. This section gives access to relevant articles featuring MADRAS published in print and digital media at a local, national, and international level. For more information on articles published see *section 5*.

The section will be continuously updated with more articles related to the project.

MADRAS IN THE NEWS

	November, 2020 <i>OAE - OPE Journal</i> Nano inks with novel functionalities (English)
	November 5, 2020 <i>Printed Electronics World</i> European consortium test new materials for organic printed electronics (English)
	October 18, 2020 <i>La Razón</i> Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa al cobre y al silicio (Spanish)
	October 13, 2020 <i>Mundoplast.com</i> Eurecat investiga nuevos materiales para plastrónica (Spanish)
	October 9, 2020 <i>Interempresas</i> Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos (Spanish)

PRESS RELEASES

European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics

The research is part of the European MADRAS project which will enable mass production of this type of electronics, known as OLAE, for accelerated time-to-market. Seen as a viable alternative to conventional electronics, OLAE devices include organic electronics printed on flexible surfaces such as plastic or paper. Their applications range from producing smart packaging, roll-up...

[Read more >](#)

Figure 8: View of "Media" page

2.2.2 Newsletters & Promotional materials

This section was created around M10 (January 2021) once the project's promotional materials were validated and ready to be shared through all the communication channels.

The page also includes a section with general information about the upcoming newsletters and a banner to facilitate the subscription. This page will be updated by publishing all the newsletters produced.

PROJECT NEWSLETTERS

Interested in keeping up to date on MADRAS progress?
Subscribe now to MADRAS community of interest and receive the projects latest news directly in your inbox.

PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Figure 9: View of “Newsletters & Promotional materials” page

3. Promotional materials

EUT has designed and produced different types of promotional materials, including an **infosheet**, **rollup**, **trifold**, **factsheet template**, **poster layout**, **general presentation** and a **video** focused on project’s topics.

All materials follow the project’s Visual Corporate Image guidelines and are available to all consortium in a digital format, so they can be shared and used every time a partner carries out a dissemination activity.

Additionally, a new section on MADRAS’ website has been created to include and share some of the promotional materials produced (rollup, info-sheet, trifold, and general presentation). Download them in “[Newsletters & Promotional Materials](#)” section on the website.

3.1 Project general presentation

In order to support the communication of the MADRAS project, a power point presentation has been prepared. Each partner is able to add new slides and complete the presentation according to their needs and to the event to be attended and/or audience.

The general presentation designed provides a general overview about the project, its main objectives, and expected impacts, the two MADRAS’ demonstrators and general information related to Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE), as well as In-Mould Electronics (IME).

Figure 10: View of MADRAS power point general presentation

3.2 Info-sheet

An A-4 info-sheet based on the main key outputs of the project, the expected results and the two demonstrators has been produced and shared through the project's website.

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS

MADRAS

MADRAS's main objective is to boost the production of organic and large-area electronics (OLAE) establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology with new materials based on in-mould hybrid and printed electronics (IME).

The project is developing low cost and reliable materials for a high-volume production of flexible plastronic products.

With the combination of two different manufacturing processes such as printed electronics and injection moulding and thermoforming, MADRAS project will develop an innovative and scalable manufacturing methodology to improve OLAE-devices durability and reduce production costs.

MADRAS is conceived to enable the future market deployment of flexible and wearable OLAE-based products.

COST COMPETITIVENESS
Cost reduction of 30% due to an increased manufacturing yield when compared with non in-moulded devices.

PROCESSABILITY
Development of transparent conducting inks and paper-based substrates.

DURABILITY
Enhanced device lifetime thanks to the application of robust materials and encapsulation.

EASIER ASSEMBLY PROCESS
New manufacturing platform based on a modular approach that allows rapid industrial production of devices.

MADRAS DEMONSTRATORS

A NEW BIOMETRIC PHOTSENSOR
Fingerprint biometric reader based on photodetection for users' identification.

A NEW GEOTRACKING FLEXIBLE TAG
Flexible tag to be attached to objects such as tools, vehicles and parts in assembly lines.

MADRAS

CONSORTIUM

eurecat, eticas, GENESiX, OCPV, TNO, arjowiggins, CDC, TecniP, TNO, UNE, UWINLOC

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019722

Figure 11: MADRAS info-sheet

3.3 Rollup

Two different versions of a project rollup have been produced to be used when attending dissemination events and/or to share through MADRAS' communication channels.

Figure 12: View of the two versions of the rollups designed

3.4 Trifold

A trifold describing MADRAS project has been elaborated during the first months and shared to all consortium.

This document contains an introduction to the project, the main objectives, key outputs, methodology, demonstrators, and general information related to Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE).

NEW MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING PROCESSES FOR A SCALABLE PRODUCTION OF ORGANIC LARGE AREA ELECTRONICS (OLAE) DEVICES

MADRAS project is conceived to enable the future market deployment of flexible and wearable OLAE-based products.

The project aims to boost the production of **Organic and Large-Area Electronics (OLAE)** establishing a high-speed manufacturing methodology with new materials based on in-mould hybrid and printed electronics (IME).

The main innovation behind MADRAS relies on developing advanced materials to be promptly processed via IME to fabricate a new generation of plastronic products with enhanced properties to make OLAE-based devices more affordable and durable.

MADRAS

MORE INFORMATION
www.madras-project.eu
gr@madras-project.eu
<https://twitter.com/madrasproject>

MADRAS

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSING IN ORGANIC ELECTRONICS

MADRAS

Next generation of plastronic products

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 802462

MADRAS KEY OUTPUTS

- COST COMPETITIVENESS**
Cost reduction of 30% due to an increased manufacturing yield when compared with non in-moulded devices.
- PROCESSABILITY**
Development of transparent conducting inks and paper-based substrates.
- DURABILITY**
Enhanced device lifetime thanks to the application of robust materials and encapsulation.
- EASIER ASSEMBLY PROCESS**
New manufacturing platform based on a modular approach that allows rapid industrial production of devices.

PRODUCTION METHODOLOGY

A new device manufacturing process combining injection moulding and printed electronics

MADRAS will develop an innovative and scalable manufacturing methodology to improve OLAE devices durability by encapsulation and reduce device manufacturing costs and high productivity rates.

ORGANIC AND LARGE AREA ELECTRONICS (OLAE)

Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE) is a new branch of electronics that works on conductive polymers, plastics, or small molecules.

OLAE devices are made of carbon-based materials which are widely available, cheaper and less toxic than traditional silicon-based electronics and are ideal for applications that require flexibility and adaptability to large areas.

OLAE devices market will exponentially expand over the next ten years: growing from \$41.2 Billion in 2020 to \$74 billion in 2030 (source: IoTechEx)

MADRAS DEMONSTRATORS

Two different demonstrators of plastic-embedded printed electronics

A NEW BIOMETRIC PHOTOSENSOR
Fingerprint biometric reader based on photodetection for users' identification.

A NEW GEOTRACKING FLEXIBLE TAG
Flexible tag to be attached to objects such as tools, vehicles and parts in assembly lines.

MADRAS PROJECT TIMELINE

- Materials improvement
- Design and printing of materials and control circuits
- Demo products manufacturing
- Validation and demonstration of materials
- Processing and demonstrators in relevant environments

Figure 13: MADRAS trifold

3.5 Poster Layout

A poster layout has been designed to be used and adapted by all partners when they need it. The document includes guidelines on how to structure the content and information along the poster.

Figure 14: MADRAS poster layout

3.6 Factsheet template

A factsheet template has been created to share relevant MADRAS’ deliverables on project’s website and also through the Zenodo Community in order to show results and impacts achieved by the project.

This document, available to all consortium, presents a guideline on how to include and structure the main deliverable information and visual elements, along the factsheet.

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND
PROCESSING IN ORGANIC
ELECTRONICS

Factsheet - DATE dd/mm/yyyy

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Introduction / Executive summary

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Methodology / solution description

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Insert representative image / graph

Conclusions / results

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HIGHLIGHTED SENTENCE:
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www.madras-project.eu

[@MADRAS_Project](https://twitter.com/MADRAS_Project)

info@madras-project.eu

The project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 862492

Figure 15: MADRAS factsheet template

3.7 Video

In what regards to audio-visual materials, a video was produced on general information of the project and the process of in mould integration of printed flexible photodetectors.

The video, which has been realised by INF, with EUT support, presents some preliminary results of in mould integration of a printed/coated flexible photodetector.

This video has been shared through MADRAS' Twitter account and has been published also in project's YouTube channel. See the video [here](#).

Figure 16: View of the video produced and shared on YouTube channel

4. Social Media

EUT is managing MADRAS' social media accounts, including a Twitter profile ([@MADRAS_Project](#)) and a [YouTube channel](#).

Partners contribute to spreading the word through their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook or Instagram.

The project coordinator is responsible for notify the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

4.1 Twitter

MADRAS' Twitter account is managed by EUT with the support of project partners for the correct management of the profile.

Twitter account serves to inform about the project development to European institutions, engage with members in the scientific community and industrial professionals and promote the use of social media complicities between MADRAS and its sister projects, such as SmartEEs, PeroCUBE, INNPAPER, 5E Project, RoLA-FLEX or HI-ACCURACY, among others.

Figure 17: View of MADRAS Twitter Profile

EUT creates monthly a content plan with different types of publications to be disseminated through the MADRAS Twitter account. Additionally, all partners can propose new content to be distributed through this channel.

The different posts published include: content curation with news and information related to project's topics, events in which partners have participated, dissemination of consortium meetings, promotion of the newsletter sign-up form created, distribution of the promotional materials and the press release produced, and other news related to MADRAS, among others.

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

Stay up to date on the progress of #MADRAS project!

Be one of the first ones to subscribe to our community of interest

cutt.ly/Pj08i2f

Horizon 2020 and 9 others

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

Are you interested in #MADRAS @EU_H2020 funded project?

Find out more about #OLAE products, #InMouldElectronics and #PrintedElectronics with our new promotional materials!

cutt.ly/2k8Vbu9

infinityPV and 9 others

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

#OLAE is a new branch of #electronics allowing thinner, more power-efficient, flexible and lightweight devices.

#MADRAS project validates a novel technology for their mass production combining #PrintedElectronics and #InMouldElectronics

Learn more madras-project.eu/olae/

infinityPV and 8 others

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

[VIDEO] #MADRASproject consortium test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic #PrintedElectronics

Watch this video to learn more about the project

MADRAS - In mold integration of printed flexible photode... The MADRAS project aims to boost the production of organic and large-area electronics (OLAE) by establishing a high... youtube.com

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

Starting #MADRASproject 1st General Assembly to review the work done during the first 6 months of the project and plan next steps for the development of #advancedmaterials for the mass production of #OLAE #PrintedElectronics products

infinityPV and 9 others

MADRAS project @MADRAS_Project

Join the webinar organised by @Eurecat_news to learn more about future #wearables and identify new opportunities of #printedelectronics market

Wednesday 28th October
10AM
Online

REGISTER HERE

Figure 18: Examples of tweets published on MADRAS profile

At M11 (February 2021), the MADRAS Twitter account counts with **101 followers** and has generated **124 tweets** and more than **37K impressions**.

MADRAS Twitter account	M1-M11
Followers	101
Total tweets	124
Twitter impressions	37,241
Mentions	27
Likes on tweets	178
Retweets	100

Table 1: MADRAS Twitter profile data (M1-M11)

4.2 YouTube

The YouTube account was created in M4 (July 2021). [MADRAS YouTube Channel](#) has been used as a video content repository and its content links have been shared on social media and through MADRAS' website.

For the moment, the channel has **1 video published**. As mentioned in previous sections, this video gives a general overview about the MADRAS project and presents some preliminary results related to in mould integration of a printed/coated flexible photodetector.

At M11, MADRAS YouTube Channel has achieved more than **130 visualisations** and **9 subscribers**.

Figure 19: MADRAS YouTube Channel profile

4.3 Partners Channels

Partners also shared MADRAS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook, mainly), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.madras-project.eu or on MADRAS' Twitter account.

Just summing the activity in partners' corporate social media accounts, mentioned at section 4.3 of D5.11 Communication Activities, from M1-M11, partners have posted a total of **14 posts** in their corporate social media accounts, accumulating **103 likes** and **12 shares/retweets**.

Figure 20: Examples of partners' posts about MADRAS

5. Media relations

During M1-M11, MADRAS Communication leader EUT has produced **1 press release** with general information about the project and its consortium, which has been **distributed to all partners and adapted to several languages**.

EUT has written this first press release with the inputs of all the project's partners, which have validated all the content before sending it to the media outlets.

Additionally, EUT has identified, and will be continuously identifying general and specialised media contacts to send the press release and spread the word about the project to society in general.

The press release produced had an important impact on online and print media. As a result, MADRAS project has been featured in **10 Spanish and English media outlets at regional, national, and international level**, including OAE-OPE Journal, Printed Electronics World, La Razón, MundoPlast and Interempresas, among others. *See Annex 9.1 for a complete list of articles featuring MADRAS.*

- **Consortium press release:** [European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics](#)

The screenshot shows the MADRAS website's news section. The main article is titled "European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics" and is dated October 8, 2020. The article features a photograph of a person using a pen to draw a circuit on a flexible surface. Below the photo, there are several bullet points:

- The research is part of the European MADRAS project which will enable mass production of this type of electronics, known as OLAE, for accelerated time-to-market.
- Seen as a viable alternative to conventional electronics, OLAE devices include organic electronics printed on flexible surfaces such as plastic or paper.
- Their applications range from producing smart packaging, roll-up displays and flexible solar cells to single-use diagnostic devices and printed batteries along with other innovations.

The article also includes a short paragraph: "The European MADRAS project is to develop new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into plastic parts for..."

On the right side of the page, there is a "Recent Articles" section with three entries:

- Genesink disseminates MADRAS project at the International Workshop on "CRM Innovations Frontiers"
- European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for organic printed electronics
- MADRAS takes part in the Digital Showcase of the SE Project
- MADRAS project Kicks Off!

Figure 21: Press release published on MADRAS website. See the full text [here](#)

On the other hand, as showed in following figures, some partners have adapted and published the consortium press release in their corporate webpages.

Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos

El centro tecnológico **Eurecat** coordina el proyecto europeo **MADRAS**, que desarrollará nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación para la producción escalable a nivel industrial de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos, también conocidos como **dispositivos OLAE**, integrados en piezas plásticas con el objetivo de facilitar su llegada al mercado.

En conjunto, los avances en el ámbito de la electrónica impresa y materiales han abierto la puerta a la creación de productos con nuevas funcionalidades, más ligeros, más delgados y más flexibles, por lo que han facilitado el desarrollo de esta tecnología y la proliferación de aplicaciones para diferentes sectores.

En este sentido, los dispositivos orgánicos se consideran una alternativa viable a los conductores inorgánicos tradicionales, como el cobre o el silicio. Su funcionamiento incorporará la electrónica orgánica impresa sobre superficies flexibles como plásticos o papeles, para numerosas aplicaciones, entre las que figuran la producción de envases inteligentes, de pantallas enrollables, de células solares flexibles, de dispositivos de diagnóstico de un solo uso y de baterías impresas, entre otras innovaciones.

En palabras de la coordinadora del proyecto MADRAS, Rosa Araujo, project manager de Eurecat, MADRAS tiene como objetivo "demostrar una mejora de los dispositivos OLAE, estableciendo una metodología de fabricación alternativa robusta y un enfoque innovador, en un proceso competitivo escalable".

El proyecto "propone dos productos para el mercado de autenticación y fabricación inteligente, que mostrarán un avance hacia la digitalización y el Internet of Things, por su contribución al desarrollo sostenible de productos inteligentes para uso del consumidor". Estos productos "pertenecen a la tendencia emergente mundial de la electrónica estructural con mercados dirigibles muy grandes, como son el sector de la automoción y la asistencia sanitaria, entre muchos otros", añade Araujo.

Figure 22: Spanish press release published in the EUT webpage. See the full text [here](#)

Inicio > Noticias > NDP: Un consorcio europeo probará nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación para electrónica orgánica impresa

NDP: UN CONSORCIO EUROPEO PROBARÁ NUEVOS MATERIALES Y PROCESOS DE FABRICACIÓN PARA ELECTRÓNICA ORGÁNICA IMPRESA

- La investigación forma parte del proyecto europeo MADRAS que permitira la producción masiva de este tipo de electrónica, conocida como OLAE, para acelerar el proceso de comercialización.
- Considerados como una alternativa viable a la electrónica convencional, los dispositivos OLAE incluyen electrónica orgánica impresa en superficies flexibles como plástico o papel.
- Sus aplicaciones van desde la producción de envases inteligentes, pantallas enrollables y células solares flexibles hasta dispositivos de diagnóstico de un solo uso y baterías impresas, junto con otras innovaciones.

Barcelona, 08 10 2020.- El proyecto europeo MADRAS desarrollará nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación para la producción en masa escalable de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos, también conocidos como dispositivos OLAE, integrados en piezas de plástico para acelerar su comercialización (time to market).

El progreso en la electrónica y los materiales impresos ha allanado el camino para productos con nuevas características, más livianos, delgados y flexibles. Esto ha impulsado el desarrollo de la tecnología y la difusión de aplicaciones para una variedad de sectores.

Los dispositivos orgánicos se consideran una alternativa viable a los conductores inorgánicos convencionales, como el cobre y el silicio. Integran electrónica orgánica impresa en superficies flexibles como plásticos o papel para numerosas aplicaciones, incluida la producción de envases inteligentes, pantallas enrollables, células solares flexibles, dispositivos de diagnóstico de un solo uso y baterías impresas, junto con otras innovaciones.

En palabras de Rosa Araujo, directora de proyectos de Eurecat y coordinadora de MADRAS, MADRAS pretende "demostrar una mejora en los dispositivos OLAE mediante el establecimiento de una robusta metodología de fabricación alternativa y un enfoque innovador en un proceso competitivo escalable".

Figure 23: Spanish press release published on Tecnopackaging webpage. See the full text [here](#)

European consortium to test new materials and manufacturing processes for consumer electronics

8 octobre 2020 by admigenesink in Genesink news

- The research is part of the European MADRAS project which will enable mass production of this type of electronics, known as OLAE, for accelerated time-to-market.
- Seen as a viable alternative to conventional electronics, OLAE devices include organic electronics printed on flexible surfaces such as plastic or paper.
- Their applications range from producing smart packaging, roll-up displays and flexible solar cells to single-use diagnostic devices and printed batteries along with other innovations.

France, October 8th 2020: The European MADRAS project aims to develop new materials and manufacturing processes for scalable mass production of organic electronics devices, also known as OLAE devices, integrated into

Figure 24: English press release published on Genesink webpage. See the full text [here](#)

Figure 25: English press release published on Arjowiggins webpage. See full text [here](#)

6. Newsletters

EUT as MADRAS Communication Leader will produce **regular newsletters**, which will include news and updated information of the project developments to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly updated.

A sign-up form has been created in order to progressively gain more newsletter's subscribers. The sign-up form is published on the website homepage and has been promoted via social media channels.

Additionally, different materials have been prepared and are being used to promote the project's newsletter through the MADRAS communication channels, together with the sign-up form link. After the initial sign-up promotion, the project's newsletter counts with a total of 11 subscribers.

Subscriptions and De-subscriptions will be managed automatically via Mailchimp, the email marketing online platform that will be used for sending the newsletters. Data collected through the sign-up form will be used for the exclusive purpose of sending subscribers information related to the project and will never be passed to third-party companies unless there is a legal obligation to do so. The **sign-up form** created complies with the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation), linking to the newsletter privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any moment.

Figure 26: MADRAS newsletter sign up form

The screenshot shows a sign-up form for the MADRAS newsletter. At the top, there is the MADRAS logo. Below it, a heading reads: "Subscribe now to be updated on MADRAS project development and latest news on Plasronics and Organic and Large Area Electronics." The form contains three input fields: "First Name", "Last Name", and "Email Address". Below these fields, there is a section titled "I wish to receive information on:" with two checkboxes: "MADRAS project developments" and "Other related projects participated / coordinated by Eurecat". A "Privacy policy information" section follows, stating that MADRAS will use the provided information for updates and providing a link to the privacy policy. At the bottom, there is a "Subscribe" button and a Mailchimp logo.

Figure 27: Example of some images created to promote the newsletter on social media

7. Partners Communication activities

MADRAS project's partners have also done different types of communication actions with the objective of increasing awareness about the project and disseminating it through an important and large audience.

These activities include: the inclusion of the project's information on partners' website and/or newsletters, the publication of news about MADRAS on corporate social media channels, or the production of some audio-visual materials , among others.

See Annex 9.2 to see the complete list of partners' communication activities produced from M1-M11.

Figure 28: Inclusion of MADRAS information on EUT webpage. Read the full text [here](#)

Figure 29: Inclusion of MADRAS information of TecnoPackaging website. Read the full text [here](#)

Advanced materials and processing in organic electronics

MADRAS project aims to demonstrate a materials-driven improvement of OLAÉ devices, establishing a high speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process which is In Mold Hybrid Printed Electronics (IMHyPE).

Four high performance materials to be developed in MADRAS tackle high cost, instability and short lifetime of OLAÉ devices under operational conditions through the development of robust alternatives and innovative approaches. Such materials are a conductive and transparent substrate, a semiconducting transparent ink based on organic components,

Figure 30: Inclusion of MADRAS information on Genesink webpage. Read the full text [here](#)

Figure 31: Inclusion of MADRAS information at HolstCentre- TNO Research webpage. Read the full text [here](#)

8. Communication KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of MADRAS Key performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the communication activities. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M12	Target by the end of the project
Media	Number of press releases	Proof of publication and reporting in reports / project meetings	1	>2
	Number of articles published		10	>30
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytis	694	>4,000
	Number Pages Viewed		1,919	>10,000
	Number page / session		3	>1,5
	Number users		403	>2,000
	Avg. session time		4 min	>3,00 min (70% of the users)
Social Media - Twitter	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	101	>200
	Number Tweets		124	>150
	Twitter Impressions		37,241	>50,000
	Number mentions		27	>20
Social Media - YouTube	Number of videos uploaded	Proof of publication in reports	1	>2
Social Media - Partners	Number of posts in corporate channels	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	14	>20
	Number of Likes in corporate channels		103	>50

Newsletters	Number Shares / Retweets in corporate channels	12	>10
	Participation in LinkedIn groups	0	Proof of publication
	Number of Proof of publication in newsletters issued reports	0	6

Table 2: Communication KPIs

9. ANNEX

9.1 Articles published in media outlets

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Link
09/10/20	Interempresas	Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa a cobre y silicio	Online	Link
11/10/20	Factoria del Futuro	Materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos	Online	Link
13/10/20	Mundoplast.com	Eurecat investiga nuevos materiales para plastrónica	Online	Link
14/10/20	Cerdanyola.info	Eurecat assaja nous materials i processos de fabricació de dispositius electrònics orgànics impresos	Online	Link
14/10/20	Revista Plásticos Modernos	Ensayan nuevos materiales y procesos de fabricación de dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos	Online	Link
16/10/20	La Razón Digital	Dispositivos electrónicos orgánicos impresos, la alternativa a cobre y silicio	Online	Link
16/10/20	30virtual	Eurecat coordina un projecte europeu per desenvolupar nous materials i processos de fabricació de dispositius electrònics orgànics impresos	Online	Link
18/10/20	La Razón - Innovadores	ESCAPARATE DE IDEAS	Print	Link
05/11/20	Printed Electronics World	European Consortium Test New Materials for Organic Printed Electronics	Online	Link
10/11/20	OAE - OPE Journal	Nano inks with novel functionalities	Online	Link

Table 3: List of articles featuring MADRAS published in media outlets

9.2 Partners communication actions

Date	Partner	Type of dissemination action	Description	Type of audience	Link
April 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of MADRAS information into EUT internal newsletter sent to all employees	Scientific & Academic Community	NA
May 2020	EUT	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in EUT website	General Public	Link
July 2020	GNK	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in Genesink website	General Public	Link
July 2020	INF	Videovisual/ audiovisual material	In-mould process video	Industry Community	Link
Oct 2020	TNG	Inclusion project information on Website	Project page in TGN website	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	AWCP	Press release	Post of MADRAS press release in the powercoatpaper.com news	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	GNK	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on Genesink webpage	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	TNG	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on TNG webpage	General Public	Link
Oct 2020	EUT	Press release	Inclusion of MADRAS press release on EUT webpage	General Public	Link
Nov 2020	EUT	Newsletter	Inclusion of MADRAS press release into the Advanced Cluster Materials Cluster	General Public	NA
Nov 2020	GNK	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	Article in OPE Journal (pp 24-25) on GNK materials based on Ag NWs and WO3 Nano inks with novel functionalities	General Public	Link

Table 4: List of partners' communication activities